

REINFORCING MECHANISM AND A PAVEMENT APPLICATION
OF STEEL FIBER REINFORCED CONCRETE

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This paper provides an explanation for the controlling factors and its mechanism of the fracture strength of steel fiber reinforced concrete (SFRC). The experiments were done by mainly flexural test and fractography of the beams, varying many variables such as geometrical shape (aspect ratio) and volume fraction of fibers, bond strength between fibers and concrete (mortar) matrix, and the size of test beams. The results show that the fiber spacing and the total bond strength of fibers which lie on the crack propagating plane are main factors for the first crack strength and the ultimate strength respectively. The latter is markedly varied with a test beam size because the orientation of fibers differs by the size. Increasing the surface area of fibers, for example, aspect ratio, volume fraction, is also effective to the strengthening of SFRC. According to these results, 5 cm thick overlay on asphalt road became possible using SFRC.

Introduction

It has been well known that the flexural strength of concrete can be reinforced very much by steel fibers. However the detailed strengthening mechanism is not fully clarified yet, despite many investigations reported so far. The rule of mixture was universally applied¹⁻³ and it is now supported by some workers because many engineering data have a good correlation with the volume fraction of fibers in concrete.

Romualdi et al⁴ presented the spacing concept in 1963. According to their theory, the tensile strength and the first crack flexural strength vary with $S^{-1/2}$, where S is the average fiber spacing. After them, many investigations have been made on the standpoint of this fiber spacing.⁵⁻⁷ However, there is a disagreement concerning what the fiber spacing mainly affects, the first crack strength, ultimate strength, or both.

It is our object of the present paper to clearly establish the factors controlling the strength of SFRC, especially the influence of such variables as geometrical shape (aspect ratio) of fibers, volume fraction of fibers, bond strength between fibers and concrete matrix, and the size of test beams.

We used mainly the flexural test and fractography to investigate the influences of the above variables. Fractography is a useful technique for an examination of the orientation of fibers which actually participate the fracture of SFRC.

Experimental Procedure

Preparation of Test Beams

Various shaped steel fibers used in this experiment were all made with shearing from a cold steel sheet (or coil). These fibers were added to mortar or concrete, the former of which was cured in water for 7 days, and the latter for 28 days. These mix designs are shown in Table I.

Table I Size of steel fibers used and mix designs of concrete (mortar)

Steel Fiber	0.5×0.5×20~30, 0.1×1×15~40, 0.35×0.8×30, 0.8φ×1.6 mm
Mortar	C:S:W = 1:2:0.55
Concrete	C:S:A:W = 1:2:0.45:0.42

Three kinds of sizes of the test beams were used as shown in Fig. 1. The 5×5×30 cm beams were specially prepared to be cut out from a 5×30×30 cm plate.

Flexural Test

Flexural tests were carried out using center point loading on beams (1) and (2) in Fig. 1, and third point loading on a beam (3). Load-deflection curves were obtained to get first crack and peak loads as the first crack strengths and the ultimate ones respectively. Subsequently, fracture surfaces of these beams were investigated in detail to measure the lengths and the angles of steel fibers pulled out.

Bond Strength Test

The bond strength between steel fibers and matrix has a large effect on

Fig. 1 Sizes of flexural test beams.

the strength of SFRC.⁸ Then pull-cut tests were performed to know the bond strength, where a steel fiber variously surface treated was buried into mortar matrix.

Results and Discussion

Fiber Geometry and Aspect Ratio

The aspect ratio of steel fibers used in concrete is usually from 50 to 100. In this condition both the first crack strength and the ultimate strength increase as the volume fraction of fibers increases and a load-deflection curve is remarkably changed comparing with that of plain concrete as shown in Fig. 2. However the fracture strength of concrete was also increased by an addition of a large quantity of steel shot wire the aspect

Fig. 2 Load-deflection curves for (a) plain mortar, (b) SFRC ($V_f=1.5\%$, aspect ratio=60), and (c) SFRC ($V_f=30\%$, aspect ratio=2)

ratio of which was as small as 2.⁷ The load-deflection curve in this case is also shown in Fig. 2 and there is not the load increase after the first crack in this case, as in the plain concrete. Consequently, the geometry of steel fibers is an effective factor to the ultimate strength of SFRC rather than to the first crack strength. Therefore it is considered that the first crack strength is almost controlled by the properties of matrix itself. As there are many pre-existing cracks such as void in concrete matrix, the stress for propagating these cracks can be estimated by Griffith's equation,

$$\sigma = \left\{ \frac{2E\gamma}{\pi(1-\nu^2)C} \right\}^{\frac{1}{2}} = \left(\frac{2E\gamma}{\pi C} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

here, 2C is the diameter of a void.

When we use 3×10^4 MN/m² for E (Young's modulus for concrete), and suppose 1 J/m² or 10^{-1} J/m² for γ (surface energy for concrete) and 10^{-2} m or 10^{-3} m for 2C, the following results are obtained.

Table II Stresses required for the propagation of a pre-existing crack.

2C \ γ	1 J/m ²	10^{-1} J/m ²
	10^{-3} m	6.3 MN/m ²
10^{-2} m	2.0	0.6

In the case of an addition of steel shot wires, it seems that the increase in E and γ , and the decrease in 2C causes the high first crack strength. However, a little addition of steel fibers with an usual aspect ratio is also effective for the increase in the first crack strength. Then, this phenomena can be attributed to the decrease in the size of pre-existing cracks and/or the effective stress at the tip of these cracks. As the size of pre-existing cracks is approximately dependent on the fiber spacing, the concept by Romualdi et al⁴ will be verified for the increase in the first crack strength.

Bond Strength

It has been also well known that steel fibers are pulled out in the process after the first crack of fiber reinforced concrete. Only in the case that added fibers have a usual aspect ratio as shown in Fig. 2(b), the flexural load increases to the higher value than the first crack load. Therefore the ultimate strength of SFRC will be governed by the fiber pulling out process, and so by the bond strength between fibers and concrete matrix.^{9, 10} In the present paper, the effect of bond strength on the ultimate strength of SFRC was investigated.

The bond strength was altered by chemical treatments of coatings of fibers, and measured using a pull-out technique. Then the test beams added those fibers were flexurally loaded. The ultimate strength linearly increased with increasing bond strength as shown in Fig. 3.

To clarify the influence of fiber orientation on the bond strength of fibers and on the strength of SFRM, we had another experiment, where fibers were aligned to have a constant angle (θ) in a test beam as depicted in Fig. 4. After the flexural test, fracture surfaces were investigated to obtain the total pull-out areas of fibers. The ultimate strength decreased with increasing θ .

Fig. 3 Effect of bond strength between fiber and mortar matrix on the relative flexural strength of SFRM.

Fig. 4 Effect of fiber orientations on the relative flexural strength of SFRM and the index of bond strength.

$$\alpha' = \left\{ \frac{\sigma'(\theta)}{\sum n(\theta)l(\theta)} \right\} / \alpha(90^\circ)$$

$n(\theta)$ = number of fibers and
 $l(\theta)$ = length of fibers on a fracture surface.

When we took the relative ultimate strength divided by bonded area of fibers on the fracture surface as an index of bond strength, it had almost the same values, irrespectively of θ , to show that the bond strength would be independent of the fiber orientation (θ) (Fig. 4).

Fiber Orientation

As mentioned in the above results, the relative ultimate strength might be explicable by taking the total bond strength of orientated fibers on the fracture surface into account.

The total bond strength can be written as the following equation (2).

$$A = \frac{\alpha}{S} \int_0^{\pi/2} \pi d \cdot l(\theta) \cdot n(\theta) d\theta \quad \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

- α : bond strength between a fiber and matrix
- $l(\theta)$: length of fibers at θ on the fracture surface (F.S.)
- $n(\theta)$: number of fibers at θ on F.S.
- d : diameter of a fiber
- S : area of F.S.

If all fibers are randomly orientated in a test beam, $n(\theta)$ will be written as an equation (3).

$$n(\theta) = N(\theta) \frac{1}{L} \cos\theta = \frac{Nl}{L} \sin\theta \cos\theta = \frac{Nl}{2L} \sin 2\theta \quad \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

- N(θ): number of fibers at θ
in a test beam
- l : length of a fiber
- L : length of a test beam
- N : total number of fibers
in a test beam

When V_f is the volume fraction of fibers in a test beam

$$N = \int_0^{\pi/2} N(\theta) d\theta$$

$$= V_f \cdot L \cdot S / \frac{\pi}{4} d^2 l \quad \dots\dots (4)$$

However in a usual case, fibers were not randomly orientated. There was an example, where the ultimate strength increased with decreasing the size of the test beams as shown in Fig. 5. In this experiment all variables were kept constant except for the size of the test beams. Therefore, if it is assumed that the total bond strength is the main factor of the ultimate strength, it should be certified by the following particular technique.

Fig. 5 Effect of the test piece size on the relative flexural strength of SFRC.

We examined fracture surfaces of these test beams to measure the angles and lengths of fibers pulled out as shown in Fig. 6. These results are shown in Fig. 7 and Fig. 8 as a function of angle θ between a fiber and the axis perpendicular to the fracture surface. The peak value in numbers shifted down to lower angles as the size of the test beam became smaller. The lengths of fibers on fracture surface, which was pulled out after the first crack, were usually below the half length of the fiber. From these results, we were able to calculate the index of the total bond area in equation (2).

Fig. 6 Observation on fracture surface of a test beam

The results are shown in Fig. 9 comparing with the ideal result for a randomly orientated test beam, which is derived from equation (3) and the assumption that l is constant.

$$\frac{n(\theta)}{n} = \left(\frac{N1}{2L}\sin 2\theta\right) / \frac{N1}{2L} \int_0^{\pi/2} \sin 2\theta = \sin 2\theta \quad \dots\dots\dots (5)$$

The difference in the distribution of this relative index of bond area causes the difference in the ultimate strength shown in Fig. 5. When these

Fig. 7 Distributions of the density of fibers observed on fracture surfaces.

Fig. 8 Distributions of the pulled-out fibers lengths on fracture surfaces.

Fig. 9 Distributions of the relative index of bond area of fibers observed on fracture surfaces.

Fig. 10 Effect of the total index of bond area of steel fibers on the relative flexural strength of SFRC.

relative ultimate strengths are plotted with the index of total bond area of steel fibers pulled out, a linear relationship was obtained as in Fig. 10.

Pavement Application

As mentioned above, the ultimate strength of SFRC increased as the size of the test beam became smaller (thinner) because of increasing the index of total bond area. On the basis of these results, we applied SFRC for thin overlays on asphalt road. The road is in Sendai Works of Nippon Steel Metal Products Co. Ltd., which locates in Miyagi Prefecture in Japan. Its traffic condition is that 75 trucks with 10 tons of steel pipes pass every day.

The conditions of the test overlays are shown in Fig. 11. Thickness of SFRC was determined by taking the high fiber efficiency of a small test beam into consideration.

Table III shows the mix proportions of the tested concrete. These were determined after several laboratory tests.

Table III Mix proportions of the SFRC for overlay

Section	Slump cm	Air %	Proportions by weight (N/m ³)						
			Water	Cement	Sand	Coarse aggregate	Fiber CSA	Water reducing admixture	
A, B, C	5±1	5±1	2107	4773	10937	2264	1862	245	12.54
D	5±1	5±1	2107	4773	10937	2352	1568	245	12.54

Fig. 11 Layout of experimental SFRC overlay. (a) plane figure (b) sectional plans

Mixing was carried out using turbo pan mixer with the capacity of 1.5 m³. The road was paved mainly by manpower and by several simple machines because the area of the overlay was not so large.

Strain gauges were embedded at the bottom of the SFRC plate for loading test as shown in Fig. 11.

Properties of the SFRC used are shown in Table IV. These results satisfied the designed thicknesses of overlays of Fig. 11.

Table IV Properties of the SFRC used (σ_b-28)

Section	Flexural strength (N/cm ²)			Young's modulus (N/m ²)	Poisson's ratio
	15×15×53 cm	5(30)×5×30 cm	4×4×16 cm		
A, B, C	755	770	1343	2.41×10 ⁶	0.22
D	670	731	1119	2.19×10 ⁶	0.23

The loading test was performed one and half a month after the pavement had been carefully cured for one week. This loading procedure is shown in Fig. 12 and the results at the center of the lane in Fig. 13.

There was a distinct difference between D and the other sections. In the D section, compressive strain was observed. This is because the SFRC was laid on the plain concrete without any bond breaker.

The overlays on the asphalt layer, which were A, B and C sections, showed similar deformation behaviors on loading. But in the A section, the load-deflection curve deviated from the straight line at about 30 N of load. At this point it seems that micro cracks initiated at the bottom of the plate. However, according to this result, the thin overlay of SFRC is able to tolerate more heavy traffic loadings even after the initiation of micro cracks at the bottom of the plate.

Fig. 12 Procedure for loading test

Fig. 13 Load-strain curves on loading of the bottom of the plate at the center of the lane.

From the results in Fig. 13, we were able to get the stresses which worked at each point. As for the stress value before the initiation of micro cracks, they were close to the calculated value under the case where the overlays deform as the asphalt-SFRC composite layers (Table V).

After one and a half years of traffic, there is no visible hair cracks at the surface of the plates.

Table V Observed and calculated stresses of the bottom of the plate at the center of the lane.

Section	A		B	C	D
Load ($\times 10^4$ N)	2.94	4.90	5.39	5.39	9.60
Loading stress (N/cm^2)	41.2	69.6	77.4	77.4	136.2
Stress observed* (N/cm^2)	317	914	530	301	-82
Stress calculated (N/cm^2)	275	505	352	307	-115

* These were estimated from the load-strain curves in Fig. 13.

Conclusions

After a series of experiments were done on steel fiber reinforced concrete (SFRC), we obtained some conclusions in the following.

1. When a large amount (30 v/o) of steel fibers with the aspect ratio as small as 2 were added to mortar, the fracture strength increased more than that of plain mortar. However, since the load-deflection curve was entirely the same as that of plain mortar, this increase can be considered to correspond to the increase in the first crack strength.

2. When steel fibers with the aspect ratio larger than about 50 were added, the flexural behavior of a SFRC beam was characterized by additional load increase after the first crack. This is probably because, in this process, steel fibers resist for cracks to propagate, and cause many micro cracks to initiate in the concrete matrix.

3. The ultimate flexural strength will depend on the abrupt release of

the bond between fibers and matrix, and linkage of many cracks. Therefore, the ultimate strength increases with increasing the total bond area of fibers pulled out.

4. The ultimate strength increases as the size of a test beam became smaller. This is because the efficiency of fibers increases and the total bond area of fibers concerned with fracture increases.

5. On the standpoint of the above conclusions, thin overlay became possible on conventional asphalt road. Such an experimental project was successfully carried out.

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